

EVOLUTION OF ESP AS THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR PROFESSIONAL PURPOSES IN UZBEK
NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: The article considers the issue of ESP evolution in foreign language teaching at non-linguistic universities. On the base of ESP and CLIL comparative analysis, the authors substantiate the shift to subject-oriented FL teaching that contributes to formation of FL professional communicative competence of a specialist. The content of a professional didactic competency of non-linguistic university EPP teacher is considered.

Keywords: CLIL, ESP, Language for Specific Purposes, LSP

The issue of the effectiveness of teaching a language for professional purposes for the development of foreign language professional communicative competence of future specialists has long been of concern to researchers of the problems of foreign language education in non-linguistic universities. The linguistic, linguodidactic, pragmatic, psycholinguistic and methodological aspects of teaching a foreign language used in a specific (professional) area of human activity are considered.

In the last decade, a number of factors have emerged that directly or indirectly influence the change in the paradigm of foreign language training of a specialist. Among these factors, one can single out the competence-based approach to training specialists, which involves designing curricula based on learning outcomes expressed in the form of formed competencies. However, regular updating of regulatory requirements for foreign language training of a specialist (currently presented by the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education 3+) does not make the task of choosing effective approaches to foreign language professional training easier, since There are a number of contradictions in the above-mentioned requirements that differentiate the language education of bachelors and masters in a non-linguistic university. In this regard, today the most pressing issues are the development of university methods of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities, with the help of which the foreign language professional communicative competence (FLPCC) of a spec The requirements for foreign language education in a non-linguistic university are regulated by the Model Program for Foreign Languages for Non-linguistic Universities, developed in 2009 and edited by S.G. Ter-

Minasova, in which the fundamental approach is recognized as Language for Specific Purposes (LSP) [1]. Several years have passed since the compilation of this program, it seems appropriate to trace the evolution of the widely known LSP approach in order to determine new teaching strategies in a non-linguistic university. The study of “language for specific purposes” (in Western terminology, Language for Specific Purposes – LSP), like the history of bilingual education, dates back to ancient times. Communication using language for specific purposes arose simultaneously with the division of labor, which entailed the emergence of different areas of knowledge and, accordingly, new concepts. The subsequent division of scientific disciplines (disciplinarity of education) and the increase in the number of specializations led to a new vector of LSP development, thanks to which the concept of “language for specific purposes” has become widely known since the 1960s of the 20th century to the present day.

LSP researcher T.N. Khomutova identifies historical (pragmatic), linguistic and linguodidactic reasons for the evolution of the concept of language for specific purposes in the second half of the 20th century [2]. During this period, LSP was going through another stage of its development, which was influenced by the end of World War II and the post-war economic recovery. The surge in economic activity and scientific and technological progress in the 1960s against the backdrop of the growing influence of the United States led to the strengthening of the role of English as the language of international communication, which led to the emergence of a new variety of the LSP approach – ESP (English for Specific Purposes).ialist will be formed. T. Hutchinson and A. Waters, considered the founders of the ESP approach, argued that the development of ESP was also influenced by the shift in emphasis in linguistics from the formal characteristics of languages to the situational contexts in which communication occurs [3]. Shifts in the linguistic paradigm led to a change in the linguodidactic aspects of ESP teaching, when T. Hutchinson and A. Waters substantiated the need to create methods that would allow teaching a language for specific purposes based on an analysis of the needs of students. Today, the theoretical development of the LSP concept is proceeding in two main directions: linguistic and linguodidactic. In the linguistic context, the LSP theory is based on the study of speech productions in the process of human communication and is implemented “in oral and written discourse in the form of texts, each of which accumulates and stores special knowledge” [4, p. 97]. In linguistics, the term LSP has many interpretations, which leads to a certain

terminological inconsistency, relating language for specific purposes to the concepts of “sublanguage”, “functional style”, “genre”, “register”, etc. This confusion is associated with the opposition of LSP and language for general purposes, adopted in the 1960s. In modern linguistics, LSP has acquired the status of a subsystem of natural language, which not only eliminated such opposition, but also led to the justification of the similarity of languages for specific and general purposes. Thus, the sources of LSP vocabulary can be words of the literary language, borrowings, slang, digital symbols, etc.; the morphological and syntactic characteristics of LSP also do not have fundamental differences from those in the language for general purposes. The specificity of LSP text genres imposes certain restrictions on the compositional structure of the specialized texts themselves (financial report, feasibility study, business letter, etc.), which allowed researchers to identify different levels of LSP text language (languages of technical, fundamental, humanities, language of material production, etc.). With the development of computer technologies, the interest of linguists in the text structures of LSP has led to the emergence of LSP studies within the framework of corpus linguistics. Today, the linguistic aspects of LSP are studied in the field of contrastive linguistics, lexicology, sociolinguistics, translation theory, and psycholinguistics.

The linguodidactic aspect of LSP is the subject of many studies in the field of foreign language teaching methods and the theory and methodology of (higher) professional education. The methodology of LSP in its most widespread version ESP was first outlined in 1987 by T. Hutchinson and A. Waters in the book “English for Specific Purposes / A Learning Centered Approach” [3]. Later, the linguodidactic concepts of ESP were developed in the book by T. Dudley-Evans and M.D. St. John “New Developments in English for Specific Purposes. Interdisciplinary approach” (1998, 2011) [5], which presents the main provisions of this direction:

- ESP is considered by scientists as an approach, and not as a product, which means that the focus of the research is not linguistic, but linguodidactic aspects;

- the analysis of the needs of students is the starting point in the construction of professionally oriented courses for teaching foreign languages to specialists;

- ESP does not provide for the study of grammatical forms that are already known to students at a basic level, but is the formation of grammatical skills necessary for certain situational contexts;

– ESP is characterized as a language limited by situations of professional communication, within the framework of which a special professionally oriented course is built;

– an ESP course can be specially designed for specific disciplines;

– ESP programs are often created for intermediate or advanced level students, but can also be developed for students at a beginner level of language training [5, p.5]; – ESP reflects the methodology typical for teaching the studied specialized disciplines;

– when teaching ESP, the teacher may ask the student for an explanation of any phenomenon typical for the specialized discipline.

Since the late 80s of the 20th century, the ESP direction has been actively developing, flexibly following the needs of the market. ESP courses are offered both as part of university programs for foreign students, and separately, on a commercial basis. Professional English-language communication skills in specialized areas are supposed to be mastered in such courses as: “English for Lawyers” (English for Legal Purposes), “English for Doctors”, “English for Air Traffic Controllers”, “English for IT specialists”, etc. The target audience of such programs is university students or certified specialists who need to develop their professional foreign-language communication skills.

Given the linguistic focus of the ESP method, the strategy for assessing students' achievements in ESP programs is generally based on the same methodological techniques as in teaching English for general purposes. The focus of the assessment procedure in ESP is professional foreign language competence, which means students' mastery of the basics of genre, discourse, grammar and terminology characteristic of a given professional field, as well as communicative competence or the ability to communicate in a foreign language in formal and informal situations. The formal method for assessing performance in an ESP classroom, as well as in a GE classroom, is written testing.

The ESP teacher is a conductor of knowledge about the language being studied, genre, discourse and terminology and does not act as a source of special knowledge (“primary knower”), since he/she is not a specialist in the content of the subject discipline. The role of the teacher in the ESP methodology is defined as “manager”, “facilitator”, “consultant”, “advisor”. The ESP methodology requires the teacher to be able to conduct a needs analysis, understand the basic concepts, and have a basic understanding of the subject matter. ESP teacher training abroad is carried out on the basis of continuing education programs,

which are widespread and accessible in many European countries, as well as on the basis of master's degree programs at universities. ESP teacher training programs are also appearing in Russia (for example, at MISiS).

In the last decade, the European practice of teaching foreign languages has shifted its emphasis towards subject-oriented teaching of foreign languages. The CLIL approach, which combines the study of a subject discipline and a foreign language used as a tool for acquiring subject knowledge (vehicular language), is a reflection of the EU policy, which promotes bilingual education as a way of convergence of European countries.

The idea of the approach is based on the language acquisition theory of C. Krashen and lies in the fact that a specially methodologically coordinated teaching of a subject discipline and a foreign language (in some cases in a foreign language) not only promotes the successful acquisition of both subjects, but also significantly develops the cognitive skills of students by establishing various neural connections in the brain [6]. Numerous experiments have proven the correctness of this assumption, which has led to its expansion in school education in the countries of the European Union, Asia and Latin America. The approach is also successfully applied in a number of European universities.

The basic concept of CLIL is the so-called "4 Cs": content - the content of the subject discipline; communication - oral and written communication in the specialty; cognition - knowledge, i.e. the development of cognitive abilities of students in the process of studying the language and a special subject; culture - a wide range of cultural context aimed at developing in students responsibility for the global and local civil society.

CLIL methodologists D. Coyle, D. Marsh, F. Hood [7] highlight the following CLIL principles:

1. Authenticity. CLIL uses authentic materials and learning situations, for example, to reproduce real-life situations.

2. Multitasking. Teaching is focused on several areas: understanding of subject content; development of cognitive skills through analysis of subject content; development of presentation and discussion skills; development of language skills (FL); formation of cooperation between students in group work mode (compliance with time frames, work with information sources); formation of skills in working with ICT. 3. Active learning. Students actively participate in the learning process both at the project preparation stage and at the presentation stage. They are responsible for involving other students in the project. They also develop peer assessment criteria and assess each other.

4. Safe learning environment. This is ensured by creating a friendly environment and equal conditions for all students, which to a certain extent echoes important psychological and pedagogical provisions on creating a comfortable environment for students in foreign language classes.

5. Scaffolded instruction. Based on the concept of the “zone of proximal development” by L.S. Vygotsky, J. Bruner’s idea of the need to create educational supports that are gradually eliminated as the student acquires autonomy in learning activities is implemented within the framework of CLIL as the basis for the teacher’s methodological actions [8].

Since CLIL does not impose entry requirements on students’ language skills; CLIL programs have no age restrictions, which makes them adaptable to various educational contexts. It is important to note that mastering a foreign language by students is not a priority task of CLIL. Language is not a goal, but a means of developing students' subject and foreign language competencies.

The approach is based on the concept of integration, which can be implemented in different ways. Studying a foreign language can be included in the curriculum of a special subject (for example, mathematics, history, geography, etc.). Subject content can be used in foreign language classes through cooperation between the foreign language teacher and the special subject teacher [7]

There are three known CLIL models: soft CLIL, the so-called language-led, when the emphasis is on the linguistic features of a special context, and hard CLIL, the so-called subject-led (subject-oriented), when almost 50% of the curriculum of subjects in a specialty is studied in a foreign language. The third model occupies an intermediate position and is used when some modular programs in a specialty are studied in a foreign language (partial immersion). One of the main goals of CLIL learning is the cognitive development of students based on the formation of thinking operations, which in CLIL are divided into low order thinking skills (LOTs) – the simplest thinking skills (memorization, classification, object definition, etc.), and high order thinking skills (HOTs) – high-order thinking skills (forecasting, reasoning, creative thinking, synthesis, evaluation, hypothesis building, etc.). The basis for “navigation” in the development of cognitive skills is the widely known taxonomy of learning objectives by B. Bloom [9].

According to the methodology of the approach, a CLIL teacher is a subject teacher with developed foreign language competence (at the B2-C1 level on the CEFR scale). This condition for the implementation of this approach complicates

its adaptation in educational institutions of the Russian Federation, since the number of subject teachers with a high level of foreign language proficiency is limited both in schools and universities, and their mass language training is a very lengthy process.

Nevertheless, the subject focus of CLIL, which distinguishes the approach from the usual ESP, which develops exclusively the linguistic skills of a specialist, seems to be an important methodological aspect of foreign language professional education in a non-linguistic university. Without the technical possibility of widespread implementation of CLIL, non-linguistic universities of the Russian Federation should nevertheless perceive foreign language education as language teaching for professional purposes (LFP), taught not only for the purpose of developing foreign language professional communication skills, but also for the purpose of expanding professional knowledge and forming the cognitive skills of students.

In pursuit of the task of developing the IPCC of a specialist in the context of two academic hours of a foreign language per week, a teacher of the FL should have developed special professional and methodological competence (PMC), including knowledge and skills in the field of competency-based design of educational programs based on learning outcomes; knowledge of the axiology of professionally oriented foreign language teaching and the language policy of universities in the Russian Federation; knowledge and skills in the field of professional linguodidactics (including the linguodidactic capabilities of ICT and methods of formative assessment); proficiency in methods of modeling professional activity in the process of foreign language teaching, implying the awareness of the FL teacher in the field of the specialized discipline; the ability to carry out interdisciplinary cooperation with specialized departments, etc. A key component of the PMC of a FL teacher is proficiency in methods and technologies of interdisciplinary foreign language teaching, based on the concept of scaffolded instruction (CLIL) [10]. The development of the proficiency and competence of a teacher of the linguistic and literate language, which determines the readiness to work effectively in a non-linguistic university, is possible today in the context of advanced training in the system of additional professional education [11]. Foreign language professional education in a non-linguistic (especially technical) university is an important component of training a competitive specialist for the development of the country's innovative economy. To solve this problem, it is necessary to shift the emphasis towards

productive interdisciplinary technologies for training future specialists, which requires from the teacher of the foreign language not only regular updating of professional knowledge and skills, but also a comprehensive understanding of the tasks facing higher professional education in Russia.

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